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Utilizing Pose Estimation for Human Action Optimization

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Abstract

Although Human pose estimation (HPE) is an impressive technology with abundant real-world applications and potential, some difficulties remain in this domain. These problems originate from imprecise depth estimations, given that even the most advanced algorithms estimations could deviate by a large margin from the real-world ground truth data. Another major challenge that limits the endless opportunities this technology can offer is the occlusion of body parts. Since a standard camera can only scan a 2D surface, some human joints could be occluded by other body parts. Estimating the joints without seeing them is a meaningless and error-prone approach. Especially when it comes to unique poses that do not appear in any of the datasets used to train these HPE algorithms, it seems much better to position the camera and the person where the necessary landmarks or joints are visible to the highest possible degree. When it comes to HPE, physical rehabilitation is a remarkably challenging problem to solve. Performing exercise correction based on incorrect estimations and readings could cause severe injuries and plenty of pain, unlike the case of traditional training routines. Firstly, the system will attempt to position the patient in the most suitable place to perform the exercise, given the knowledge of each exercise's maximum boundaries. Secondly, the camera and patient's positions direction will be optimized to harvest the full benefits of the HPE algorithms. Then it will guide the patient to and through the exercise. Ideally, Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques could give precise instructions. Instead, we shortcut the complexity of NLP and design a more straightforward, user-friendly approach by visualizing the expert's avatar in the environment. We can show the optimal position to place the camera and position the patient. We also offer the possibility of viewing the exercise at that particular position, which will help the patient imitate the task and possibly additional minor and straightforward verbal direction and distance corrections. Finally, there comes the need to monitor the patient exercise routine compared to an expert performing the same exercise and possibly give verbal feedback during the exercise execution in real-time and visual feedback after the exercise completion. Accomplishing such a task requires exercise error detection techniques to be developed and tested as a basis for exercise correction.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The rapid development of HPE methods due to the advancement that deep learning technologies offer in this domain has opened the door for additional advanced applications. HPE aims to detect what is known as landmarks or keypoints, which represent human joints, limbs, and essential coordinates in the human body; this technology can be applied to either static images or a stream of video frames. However, only a handful of algorithms exploit temporal information obtained from successive video frames, which might require automated pre-processing steps to ensure that the landmarks of back-to-back frames are not very different; otherwise, a jitter-like phenomena will take effect. HPE is a fundamental element in many activities, ranging from human pose classification from a static image and activity recognition of a sequence of consecutive frames to monitoring and quantifying physical exercises for possible corrections. Medical applications require even greater precision than the one needed in other applications. Therefore a comprehensive study and evaluation of pose estimation algorithms are fundamental.

Numerous algorithms obtain different sets of landmarks to calculate the human pose. Then, depending on the model and dataset it was trained on, it can estimate 2D or 3D poses. Estimating 2D poses is more common because it is easier than 3D poses giving the availability of the datasets and the difficulty of acquiring 3D pose point clouds from sensor devices; therefore, more algorithms are available for 2D pose estimation than its counterpart. There are many possible usages of such technology, including human-machine interaction, virtual and augmented reality, Human action

analysis and recognition, exercise monitoring and correction, and medical assistance [1, 2], especially in a rehabilitation scenario. Nonetheless, many challenges face the development of this technology, such as insufficient training data, especially when it comes to 3D poses. This type of data is harder to acquire and annotate and is more likely to be obtained in a controlled environment with the help of wearable sensors or multiple cameras carefully placed in predefined locations with possible sensor fusion with depth detectors. The second issue is occlusion, whether by objects in the scene or more likely by the person's own body. Most cameras only provide a 2D view of the scene resulting in imprecise depth estimation. Therefore with all of these challenges, there comes the need to bypass such bottlenecks rather than attempt and solve them, as they may prove to be unsolvable using only one camera. After all, logically speaking, humans cannot witness what they cannot see, nor do the cameras. In the case of medical rehabilitation, we hypothesize that it is possible to place the patient and the camera relative to each other and the surrounding environment in such a manner where the most critical joints, limbs, or any other body parts for a particular exercise are absolutely visible. Hence, avoiding or minimizing the occlusion problem, eliminating one of the most significant struggles of this technology for this project in particular. It is also worth mentioning that HPE methods have two broad categories: single person or multi-person approaches. However, any of them would work for our purposes as we only expect one person to be present at the scene's center.

1.2 Goal & Vision

This work aims to collaborate with different experts in the medical rehabilitation domain to reduce the cost and save time for the patient and the overwhelmed therapist. Furthermore, to create a deployable system from the patient's residence instead of taking the trip to the rehabilitation center, especially when the problem does not require full-time monitoring, such as in the case of full-body rehabilitation. The long-term objective of the overall project is to facilitate and assist both parties, the extremely busy experts and the unprivileged patients, under some cost and time constraints. The thesis contributes to solving the problem at hand. However, it does not give a complete solution on its own. Instead in this work, we will focus on particular areas and attempt to solve them by taking a case study of knee rehabilitation scenarios and proceeding through the crucial phases of the suggested system. The

system should generalize to other situations with little to no modifications. We also performed multiple studies to find the best approach for every part in the pipeline, from the HPE process to the more demanding error detection and exercise correction methods. Here we summarise the suggested stages in a nutshell.

- HPE and volumetric avatar construction.
- Optimizing the camera and patient position for a given exercise in a particular environment.
- Guiding the patient to the exercise position using visual and verbal instructions.
- Comparison of the perfect exercise execution process performed by the expert with the patient's performance to detect errors.

Some of the drawbacks that we faced in implementing the suggested pipeline are (a) the imprecision factor in the 3D HPE models, where the error rate could range from a few centimeters to a couple of meters, depending on the patient's distance from the camera. This issue can be solved by providing a preferred distance range and optimizing it for each exercise and HPE algorithm. As long as depth estimation between the relative position of the keypoints is below the acceptable error threshold, it should not be a significant concern anymore. (b) Some of the body parts, such as the limbs and joints, might be occluded by other body parts from the camera's viewpoint; this issue can be avoided by the placement strategy that we have implemented. It is also possible to solve by issuing a few commands in real-time from the camera's perspective to the subject. (c) The accuracy of the deep learning-based HPE algorithms heavily depends on the data and architecture used to train the methods. It might not be a big deal; however, even the slightest deviation from the mean could result in severe injuries especially in the medical assistance domain. Therefore finding what HPE method yields the best results is critical, and a detailed review and examination of these methods for the rehabilitation dataset is needed. (d) The real-time assumption might be hard to achieve at all phases of the pipeline. Also, this highly depends on the HPE algorithm, and making any trade-off to speed up the process may lead to unwanted loss of precision. Therefore, it is essential to do anything that can be achieved offline beforehand and carefully select

a frame rate that does not reduce the model accuracy but helps the system reach real-time performance.

1.3 Background & Related Work

There is no shortage of techniques in the computer vision domain using landmarks detection algorithms and the relatively new deep learning methods regarding pose estimations. Since the deep learning-based methods far exceed the traditional ones in every way possible, we will only focus on them and attempt to find the most suitable one for the rehabilitation scenario, with constraints on precision, performance, and execution speed. Regarding exercise modeling in fitness-like situations utilizing HPE methods to provide feedback for the user, only a handful of work was conducted in this domain, such as [3, 4, 5, 6]. These approaches used real-time sensors to read the 3D human pose accurately, and they appear outdated compared to the new technology that has recently emerged, so it does not work for the single-camera case. However, there were other approaches based on images and video streams, such as in the case of [7, 8, 9], whereas in [7], they tried to use multiple cameras to estimate a 3D skeleton in real-time and utilize it alongside a preconstructed expert's skeleton to attempt identifying errors in the exercise signature in comparison with the instructors signature. In addition, their system could model the 3D meshes over time, count the repetition, and provide visual and writing feedback if the subject's exercise pattern deviated from the fitness expert's pattern. Regardless, they did have to introduce a new dataset with over three million images which takes a lot of effort and resources. Furthermore, each exercise in the dataset is captured from four different angles/cameras with additional scans of the subject using a motion capturing system to obtain the ground truth labels. The deployed system can record the person performing the exercise, output the feedback, and count the repetitions. However, their repetition counter works on two frail assumptions: first, the number of repetitions is fixed before the start of the execution process, and second, that the duration of each repetition is the same as the preceding ones, where usually as the subject gets tired they will most likely slow down their pace a bit. Meaning that deploying it is a real challenge, and therefore this technique cannot work for our case, where we assume that the user either has a standard camera, RGB-depth, or stereo camera. Nevertheless, we will focus on the most common but most challenging task

of a standard 2D camera and elevate the method to take the depth estimation into account and utilize multiple cameras simultaneously. [8] Proposes a deep learning framework trained on annotated data to provide a personalized athletic training experience. They aimed for activities where the human pose plays a significant role in determining the quality of execution. Their system predicts 2d human body poses in outdoor sports videos such as skiing, constructs association between them based on the temporal information obtained from the consecutive frames, and provides training suggestions for incorrect poses. Their biggest challenge revolved around the fast movement in such sports. Therefore, they heavily depend on tracking algorithms and temporal information to make up the difference between the frames. In contrast, we assume the exercise execution is done in a controlled environment. The motion is relatively slow, so we can afford to drop a few frames without compromising the model’s accuracy. They also provided the analysis only for 2D HPE, meaning it might lack precision; however, it was not a significant issue for this case as their application was not precision compromised. Nevertheless, This approach neither operates in the temporal domain nor provides interpretable feedback based on the detected errors. It only provides related examples based on the recognized pose estimation. [9, 10] proposes a visual feedback method based on OpenPose landmarks and human models reconstruction systems using SMPL [11] body models. In a single monocular image from a given exercise, the subject’s landmarks are used to fit an SMPL body shape, then compared to a correct pre-constructed reference shape. The visual feedback consists of displaying both volumetric poses on top of each other in the same frame on a specially designed interface, meaning oversized models (models that attempt to reconstruct the human shape with the correct scale and shape) might compromise the comparison accuracy. The drawback of the system is that it only compares a pose to another, not the sequence of consecutive poses that would make up the exercise routine. Furthermore, it cannot achieve real-time performance as processing each frame takes a considerable amount of time, around two seconds. Therefore, it is more suited to correct poses, such as yoga rather than exercises, or be applied offline for overall feedback. [12] They proposed a new approach to directly utilize the body motion information in the heatmaps-based HPE approach to acquire a system capable of utilizing action recognition and iteration counting. Heatmap methods have been proven effective in extracting dynamic body pose information. In order to achieve that goal, they also introduced a new dataset

to measure the accuracy and evaluate their system on it. However, although their approach aims towards exercise recognition, it does not tell much about the accuracy and correctness of the execution of that particular workout; it only distinguishes it from others. Therefore, it is unlikely to work for our case where our purpose is to detect abnormalities in the workout routines to attempt a corrective procedure. Although there is a resealable amount of work for regular exercise routines, there seem not to be many influential papers in this domain regarding physical rehabilitation. This case is mainly due to the task’s difficulty, the algorithm’s accuracy, and the minimal required confidence for a highly demanding medical exercise where the wrong move could lead to severe injuries. However, there are still a few relatively new applications in the medical and health domain. For instance, in [13], they have developed a mobility framework to assist the elderly in a full-body rehabilitation-like scenario (such as walking). They focused on understanding human actions and assessing the rehabilitation process by combining multiple readings from different sensors, recognizing intent, and establishing a natural language-based communication channel with the patients using speech understanding techniques. Their overall purpose was to establish a base for a multitask understanding of human behavior, such as speech intent recognition and generalized human activity recognition. However, their main focus was on older adults in walking situations. Therefore there were no predefined sets of complex exercise routines, and the data they provided is supposed to help the experts, not the subjects themselves (on their own). While in [14], they introduced a novel lightweight pose estimation model and utilized it in an in-home lower body rehabilitation scenario. The model is deployable on low computational devices such as smartphones, and their evaluation mechanism relies on the motion range and duration field. The lightweight employs an HRNet to receive more attention, leading to a much-undesired performance/efficiency trade-off. However, this direction is not what we are looking for in an accuracy-compromised scenario, where the chance of injury is constantly present. Some datasets emerged in this domain [15], this dataset comprises different physical rehabilitation movements. Furthermore, some work based on Human Activity Recognition (HAR) to identify the rehabilitation exercise has emerged [16], and other applications in the health domain have also appeared [17]. Therefore is possible to suggest that there is no other notable work in this domain comparable to what we are trying to do. Nevertheless, there are some common parts for sure. However, optimizing the exercise’s location

seems to be unique in a manner of speaking, as it attempts to avoid the shortcomings of human pose estimation rather than attempt to solve all of them, which might prove to be a difficult task, or at least challenging in the near future.

It is also possible to look at an exercise as a form of activity performed in an organized and more often redundant manner taking the form of sets and repetitions. However, it is still considered activity on that grounds; we will examine some methods used for activity recognition and attempt to derive a suitable technique that can be generalized and used in exercise error detection and correction, giving a suitable HPE.

Suppose we were to classify activity recognition and precision measurement techniques into three categories based on execution difficulties. Then simple activity and gesture recognition, such as hand movement, walking, and running, would be considered the easiest one to achieve and the least important one of all. A more exceedingly tricky task would be regular fitness training, and right after it, weight lifting, where deviating from the path of the best workout could deprive the user of the full benefit of the practice. However, a considerable amount of pain is involved when it comes to rehabilitation, and the wrong move could lead to severe injuries. From this reasoning, if a model works well on the most complex level, it should work even better on the more straightforward and less complex approaches. A trade-off between performance and precision could be performed to reach a more extensive target base as they can be satisfied with a bit lower accuracy.

1.3.1 Human Activity Recognition (HAR) Based Approaches

Although this task is not directly related to what we are trying to accomplish, some techniques used in the activity, gesture, and generally HPE based recognition could prove helpful and enable us to elevate the project to the next level. Therefore we will not consider approaches that utilize images directly. Instead, we will consider ones with an extracted feature extraction step in the form of pose estimated landmarks. Over the years, numerous studies have been conducted in this area; however, only deep learning approaches will be considered for simplicity and effectiveness. Some methods also heavily rely on wearable sensors. Others depend on different sensor types, vision sensors such as cameras being the most common in recent years due to deep learning capability.

Human activities use information from various sensor types, and it is often associated with determining and naming activities performed by individuals or groups of people within a given scene. HAR could focus on the movement of the entire human body or single parts, such as hand gesture recognition, used in some virtual reality and gaming applications. However, human action can be either atomic or comprised of many elementary actions executed in sequential order [18]. Therefore, the HAR system should label the same action with a constant label, giving different people acting in a different environment under different conditions and constraints. The difference between the methods needed to realize error detection and exercise correction systems is that instead of a label for the entire exercise. Instead, each time segment needs to be checked individually and compared to either a dataset of exercise using primitive techniques or a deep learning-based approach. The simplest form of this time segment is a frame instance, utilizing one flawlessly performed exercise using some sequence matching algorithms that operate on landmarks obtained from the HPE systems.

Sensor readings are usually more accurate than basic camera-produced images, with wearable sensors providing the best accuracy. Therefore, there has been considerably notable work in the domain, precisely as some of the surveys [19, 20, 21] present it, with [19] specializing in health care applications. On the other hand, vision-based or video-based systems are easier to deploy, handle, cheaper, and many more people could benefit from them, even though they might lack the precision. However, cameras are everywhere nowadays, so there is no wonder that many took this opportunity to develop applications utilizing video streams, as shown in [18, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26]. HAR is typically utilized to solve problems that do not require a near-perfect accuracy in human-computer interaction, such as augmented reality, fraud detection, video information extraction, automatic surveillance and security, and many more. Therefore, false positives could be manually checked, and it is considered more of an irritation than a serious design flaw. HAR system's purpose is to automate analyzing information obtained from various sensors to identify a human action. A Human activity (HA) refers to the movement of one or several body parts for a specific individual. This approach can be either atomic or composed of many primitive actions performed in some sequential order, as stated in [18]. The HAR output is usually operated to direct a succeeding decision-support system. HAR also includes the interaction between one or multiple people as well as the

individual interactions with the surrounding environment.

It is also worth mentioning that so many approaches utilize HPE methods because their techniques usually capture the essential features in a given image using a pre-trained model. Even though deep learning approaches typically do not need feature engineering. However, they will require an insane amount of raw data in that case, not to mention the effort, time, cost, experience, and knowledge it takes to develop an architecture capable of effectively transforming raw image pixels into usable information. Action recognition could gain the benefits of HPE methods by utilizing neural networks. Nevertheless, when it comes to sequence data, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) or more advanced architecture such as Long-Short Term Memory (LSTMs) or Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) can model temporal information of action sequences more effectively, such as in the most notable works presented in [27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34]. Moreover, many new approaches are emerging in the expanding domain of utilizing HPE for HAR. Therefore we can safely assume that such techniques would benefit future work.

1.4 Contributions

This section is dedicated to discussing the contributions of the theses in a few words.

- Conducted an in-depth literature search for pose estimation methods and reviewed some of them, then evaluated part of the revised methods to understand better how they work and why they should be used or should not be used in this project with detailed explanations in chapter 2.
- Developed the code to utilize these methods effectively with the ability to replace the HPE with ease, in case new technologies with greater accuracy have emerged.
- Constructed and implemented the algorithm for the best location placement in chapter 3 with simple visualizations.
- Developed, implemented, and utilized several methods that can be used for exercise error detection in chapter 4.

- Employ several image processing techniques as a pre-processing step for the HPE algorithm to be used in different circumstances in chapter 5.
- Add some additional ideas that can be used to improve and extend the thesis work to other domains in chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Human Pose Estimation (HPE)

HPE aims to determine important joints and limbs under the terms of landmarks or keypoints in the human body. Many algorithms emerged in this domain, and although they all have the same task at hand, the approaches are quite different, especially when it comes down to handling multi-person or single-person pose estimations. There are two distinct methods for a single-person pipeline that employ deep learning technologies: (I) regression-based methods, where it utilizes the output feature maps to regress key points directly from an input image to body joints coordinates. The problem with this approach is that directly mapping from image space to a single point for each landmark is a difficult task, especially since it is a nonlinear problem, and even the smallest difference between consecutive frames could yield different landmarks up to a small error ratio, which causes a jitter like an effect to occur. (II) Heatmap-based/detection-based approaches attempt to learn joints' relative or approximate position to generate intermediate heatmaps of landmarks such as joints for body part localization, then establish the entire skeleton by assembling these detected landmarks. The pixel value in heatmaps indicates the probability that a keypoint exists in a particular position, as summarized in some of the many reviews conducted in this domain [1, 2, 35]. The multi-person detection pipeline is split into two distinct categories into two broad methods. (I) Top-down approaches are divided into two steps, first by applying a human detection algorithm to retrieve the bounding boxes of individuals with the scene, and then one of the single-person pipelines is applied to each detected region in the image that contains the person. (II) bottom-up approaches, which have a similar concept but in a reversed order. The first step is to locate all possible landmarks for all existing people without prior

knowledge of the number of humans in the scene. After that, it groups the detected landmarks as skeletons according to the individual they represent, as elaborated in [1, 2]. Generally speaking, bottom-up approaches are faster when multiple people are present in the scene, but there have been numerous cases where landmarks are misassigned, leading to incorrect skeleton representations. Whereas in the top-down approaches case, there is a direct correlation between the number of people present in images and the execution speed of the algorithm.

HPE has been utilized in many domains, such as virtual and augmented reality and gaming systems, to facilitate software usage in gesture and emotion recognition, such as the case of sign language translation systems. It also has possible usage in an autonomous driving situation, whether to determine the driver's state by employing this technology to help interpret the vehicle's interaction with the surrounding environment and the people within its reach using a HAR system or something similar. More recently, in the fitness and medical domain, the tasks range from determining the type of the movement to effectively capturing the errors in the exercise and suggesting the appropriate corrective actions to take, which means that it is worthwhile to invest in the development and evolution of this technology, and build scalable applications based on it, due to the rapid improvement in this field. Even if the results are not satisfactory at the current moment, new high accuracy approaches and algorithms might reach the market at any time.

2.1 Types of Human Pose Models

Body modeling is an important aspect, and it is essential to distinguish between different HPE methods and the models they produce. Body models define the key-points/landmarks representation and how the limbs and joints of the human body are viewed and interconnected. There are three main categories, with the skeleton-based models being the most common and the easier to construct and analyze. The other two methods are the planner and volumetric models, where the planner method used to be popular in older technologies, but it seems that is no longer the case. Finally, the volumetric method is the most challenging one, but it visualizes a realistic representation of the human body and can be used in many scenarios instead of the actual person the model represents.

2.1.1 2D and 3D Models

While often 2D models are sufficient for most tasks related to action recognition, more sophisticated models are essential for accuracy compromised fitness and medical-based solutions, or at least in most cases. For example, most algorithms use a 2D-to-3D pose converter, thus resulting in a mere estimation that does not generalize well when deployed to the real world. Others train their models directly on 3D data. However, these datasets are pretty small and more restricted to indoor situations in comparison to the 2D dataset. In this situation, perhaps it is more beneficial to utilize the 2D landmarks instead. Finally, others use depth estimations by fusing different sensors or stereo cameras. Therefore having the depth, it is possible to correct the 3D pose or add a third dimension to the 2D pose based on the sensor's measurements.

2.1.2 Kinematic or Skeleton-Based Models

Typically used for 2D or 3D pose estimation, it represents a set of joints and limb positions and orientations between the corresponding locations, which are typically anywhere between (13-33) landmarks [2, 35]. Although these models are usually the easiest to acquire as a flexible point cloud representation, it has the distinct disadvantage of being incapable of representing the texture and the shape information of individuals, meaning that people with different sizes/widths will eventually get a model representation with the same thickness, hence the name skeleton-based model. Nevertheless, this type of model has been the most widely used given that it has the most significant number of applications, is the fastest to compute, has massive datasets, is simple enough, and most tasks do not require more complexity.

Here we will summarize the best approaches concerning their performance in terms of (accuracy, execution speed, memory requirement, scalability, and ease of use) to decide which type is more suitable for our purposes. Ideally, we would like to optimize all of these constraints. However, a trade-off is inevitable. We are considering the feedback in the previous reviews and surveys concerned in HPE employing newly developed deep learning methods [1, 2, 35] and newer or production models beyond the reach of these surveys. With consideration to the number and type of landmarks required. There are many different types of 2D human pose estimation algorithms, However, efficiently/correctly generalizing the 2D pose to 3D mesh is

a challenging task mainly due to the dataset availability and the fact that most 3D datasets are acquired using sensors meaning that the data gathering process is mainly performed in a controlled environment. Here we discuss some of the favored 3D HPE methods that we considered and utilized in our applications.

MediaPipe

[36, 37] A real-time 2D and 3D HPE for the body, face, and hand landmarks. It provides open-sourced libraries that offer fast, accurate and low-memory models. The framework is easy to use, providing an advanced model to detect and track poses in a video or a sequence of consecutive frames by assuming that the object does not shift positions significantly between back-to-back frames. Therefore, estimations from the previous frame determine the region of interest for the new frame. Their pipeline consists of a two-step model which utilizes detection, then tracking. First, it aims to locate the person's region of interest (ROI) within the frame. After that, the tracker subsequently predicts the pose landmarks and segmentation mask within the ROI using the ROI-cropped frame as input. It can output up to (33, 42, and 468 body, hands, and facial landmarks, respectively), and it achieves high performance of approximately 20 Frames Per Second (FPS) even on low computational power machines such as mobile devices. It falls under the regression models category. However, it is supervised by a combination of heatmap and an offset prediction of all keypoints.

Experiments Result with Examples

Figure 2.1: MediaPipe results for a right side view exercise routine

Figure 2.2: MediaPipe results for a simple motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.3: MediaPipe results for a semi-complex motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.4: MediaPipe results for a semi-complex motion lying down exercise routine

From the figures [2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4] we can see the result of MediaPipe execution on four different exercise routine available in the dataset. For the first exercise shown in 2.1, the camera is placed to capture the right side of the expert only, which yields a poor result in general as the left, and frontal sides of the therapist are completely occluded, meaning that the detection outcomes are sure to be inaccurate as well as the relative depth estimations. However, it can still produce relatively correct landmarks, mainly because the pose is quite common, so the model can use heuristic data to predict the occluded parts to some degree of accuracy. The segmentation shown in the figure could also be used to determine the occupancy of the subject in the image, thus relatively displaying the avatar's measurements. It is also worth mentioning that the person's semantic mask output by the algorithm could be considered similar in perspective to the planner model. In the case of the 2.2, and 2.3 figures, the camera is fixed at an angle suitable to capture most of the body parts, thus effectively increasing the efficiency of the algorithm and avoiding some of the bottlenecks; therefore, the pose estimation is of high accuracy and is suitable to be used for error detection when compared to the patient's pattern. However, in the fourth figure 2.4 the exercise requires the subject to lay down, meaning that if the camera's height strongly influences the accuracy, even more so than the angle. Also, an issue appears in this exercise for all HPE algorithms that were tested, which is an

incorrect estimation of the feet landmarks. Usually, this would not be an issue for other workouts. However, in this particular exercise, foot movement is a large part of it. Therefore we can safely assume that due to the angle, the conditions were not met, which is the reason causing the distorting in the estimation for this exercise on the used HPE methods.

OpenPose

[38, 39, 40, 41] As in the case of MediaPipe, this model is supposed to work in real-time, and it can predict landmarks for the body, hands, and face. Depending on the model and dataset of that particular architecture, the number of keypoints may differ. The latest development will yield (15, 18, or 25), 42, and 70 body, hands, and facial landmarks, respectively. It could retain accuracy and speed of approximately 22 FPS with a relatively good GPU, and given that it is a multi-person bottom-up approach, increasing the number of people will only increase the computation complexity by a little. It utilizes what they refer to as Part Affinity Fields (PAF), which is a set of vectors that encodes the orientation and location of limbs over the entire image domain; to learn body parts associated with people in a given image. However, as we will see in the results section, it sometimes suffers from imprecise landmarks assignments due to the bottom-up approach methodology, meaning that it could sometimes mistake some of the left foot landmarks for the right one and vice versa. One distinct advantage for 3D pose estimation is that OpenPose can utilize multiple views from different cameras and RGB-depth cameras to obtain highly accurate 3D meshes/skeletons.

Experiments Result with Examples

Figure 2.5: OpenPose results for a right side view exercise routine

Figure 2.6: OpenPose results for a simple motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.7: OpenPose results for a semi-complex motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.8: OpenPose results for a semi-complex motion lying down exercise routine

Given that OpenPose utilizes a top-down approach to detect human poses in a scene, then there is a probability of miss labeling the joints between the left and right body parts, especially in the case of the exercise shown in the figure 2.5 where the left part is occluded. However, for the second and third exercises shown in figures 2.6 and 2.7, the landmarks seem to be of acceptable accuracy. Nonetheless, for the case shown in 2.8, as in the case of Mediapipe, the left foot seems to be mismatched, since the landmarks labels do not reflect the state of the ground truth, this seems to be the case for all this model as well, which gives us a reason to suspect viewing angle as well as the light conditions that may have affected the video quality a little bit. However, these deep learning-based techniques are hard to interpret, and these only remain as speculations based on relative observations and HPE background.

Metric-scale truncation-robust (MeTRo) & Metric-Scale Truncation-Robust Heatmaps for Absolute 3D Human Pose Estimation (MeTRAbs)

[42, 43] MeTRAbs Is an extension to the already existing work done in MeTRo, wherein MeTRo the model could estimate only one human pose at a time in a given scene. However, the main contribution of both models is the capability to estimate the human pose outside the image boundaries. Fortunately, this includes occluded body parts as well. The method proposed in the paper presents a new approach for

extending 2D human pose estimation heat map-based approaches to 3D poses. This feat was accomplished by introducing volumetric heatmaps whose dimensions do not align with the image space. Instead, they define an independent space introduced as 3D metric space. This transformation between the image and metric spaces allows the models to directly estimate complete metric-scale poses without prior knowledge of the distance or relying on predefined heuristics. MeTRAbs introduced an extension of the previous work, which has the added value of having a differentiable combination of the 3D metric scale heatmaps with the 2D image-space to give rise to an absolute 3D pose estimation. The suggested end-to-end approach uses fully-convolutional neural networks to output MeTRo’s resulting models. The dimensions of the heatmaps are predefined to have a fixed metric extent in meters. The backbone of the fully-convolutional networks (FCN) has to implicitly discover occluded or out of bound landmarks/joints, analyze the scale cues, and learn a geometric perspective back projection in an end-to-end manner. Surprisingly this mapping could still be learned effectively using a moderate stander FCN, assuming the dataset is large enough. The MeTRo generated heatmaps can encode body parts outside the image boundaries or occluded by objects in the scene or other body parts. This approach is possible because the volume bounds for the predictions are not the same as the image bounds. Therefore, there is no need to design an independent scale adjustment step, making the pipeline extremely simple with no need for camera parameters such as the focal length nor other pose parameters such as the pose root joint distance. It is perfect for cameras where the exact focal length is hard to calibrate, such as mobile devices. On the other hand, utilizing the parameters can increase the depth estimation accuracy. MeTRAbs extends the previous work to utilize the effectiveness of the generated heatmaps for absolute 3D poses estimation, where it is essential in a multi-person scene, in order to recover the spatial layout of the whole group for each individual with respect to each other locations in the 3D metric space giving the 2D image space. By combining them in a two-headed CNN architecture to establish the positions of the roots in a differentiable manner, this approach is to be a supervised end-to-end pose estimation task. Moreover, it works in a top-down fashion with a predefined person detector model. It is also worth noting that this approach achieved state-of-the-art results on various datasets without any notable deterioration in execution speed compared to other methods.

Experiments Result with Examples

Figure 2.9: MeTRAbs results for a right side view exercise routine

Figure 2.10: MeTRAbs results for a simple motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.11: results for a semi-complex motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.12: MeTRAbs results for a semi-complex motion lying down exercise routine

For Metrabs, the skeleton seems to be of decent quality, and as it is noticeable in the first exercise shown in figure 2.9 where the hands in some of the frames are outside the boundaries of the camera's viewpoint, but the model could still predict with some degree of error the missing landmarks. There seems to be no notable difference from the other algorithms for the other exercise, so the excises shown in figures 2.10, and 2.11 also seem to obtain the best accuracy due to their relatively good angle. Finally, the last one 2.12 seems to have the same shortcomings as the

other models, which supports our initial conclusion about the viewing angle and possibly the height of the camera.

2.1.3 Planner or the Contour-Based Models

It is used only for 2D pose estimation extended from the skeleton model to represent the relative shape of the body in a 2D plane. It has been widely used in old techniques where the human shape contour represents body parts such as limbs as rectangles. [2, 35]. Given that we did not use them and to our knowledge, there are no deep learning-based approaches that utilize them, and then we will not discuss them any further.

2.1.4 Volumetric or Avatar-Based Models

It could be thought of as the generalization of the planner model to 3D representations, overcoming the kinematic and Planner model's shortcomings to represent a replica of the human body. Over the years, there have been several volumetric models, including the earlier models such as Shape Completion and Animation of People (SCAPE) [44], Skinned Multi-Person Linear model (SMPL) and its variations (SMPL-H) (SMPL-X) [11], Unified Deformation Model ADAM [45], Generative 3D Human Shape and Articulated Pose Models (GHUM & GHUML) [46] There are several categories of methods capable of estimating and a fully expressive 3D human for a single RGB image. They are utilizing SMPL/SMPL-H/SMPL-X, GHUM/GHUML, and ADAM. However, these methods are slow and might get stuck in a local minimum giving that they are optimization-based. Here are some of the most noticeable avatar-based models:

SMPLify and SMPLify-X Expressive Body Capture: 3D Hands, Face, and Body from a Single Image

[47, 48] This particular model introduces the ability to capture expressive 3D models of human poses from a single RGB image. They have also extended SMPL to SMPL-X by incorporating the hands, faces and improving the general body structure. The project objective was to build a model that can learn to regress the keypoints/landmarks or parameters of SMPL-X. Given that it is challenging, an extension on SMPLify extends 2D features and optimizes the model's parameter to

fit these extracted features. The improvement was to fit the SMPL-X models by features extracted from the entire human body, including the hands, face, and feet. In addition, they added a new interpolation penalty to increase the model's overall accuracy and employed a gender detector to use the appropriate base model from a subset of three predefined SMPL-X models (male, female or neutral). Furthermore, speed up the computation in general. The model utilized OpenPose 2D landmarks for the model fitting process. Moreover, Given that it is an optimization-based method, the resulting mesh should have the person's exact shape (width and height) to a certain degree of accuracy, meaning that it attempts to reproduce the curves in the human body, which might be helpful in some applications where the actual size of the subject is of significant value.

Experiments Result with Examples

Figure 2.13: SMPLify-X results for a right side view exercise routine

Figure 2.14: SMPLify-X results for a simple motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.15: SMPLify-X results for a semi-complex motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.16: SMPLify-X results for a semi-complex motion lying down exercise routine

The figures [2.13, 2.14, 2.15, 2.16] display the results of the first examined volumetric base algorithm SMPLify-X. Whereas in the first figure 2.13, we can see the results of an exercise routine shown from the instructor’s right side, meaning that some OpenPose landmarks might be inaccurate and straight-up incorrect. This issue would cause deformations in the resulting model, as it relies on the landmarks provided by OpenPose. This deformation would not be an issue for the exercises taken from a relatively good angle where most of the landmarks related to the exercise are clearly visible, as shown in the other exercises in figures [2.14, 2.15] where the resulting meshes are of higher accuracy giving that the limbs are clearly visible, there are some mistakes when it comes to the left hand. However, it does not af-

fect the overall performance of the exercise routine, especially since the focus is on the lower part of the body. In the last figure 2.16 in some of the frames, the left hand is occluded, meaning that the camera should be set higher to avoid this issue altogether. Nonetheless, other volumetric algorithms seem to handle this problem better, but it is still not completely fixed and does not reach the required level of accuracy for medical applications.

EXpressive POse and Shape rEgression (ExPose)

[49] In contrast to other methods, which are optimization-based, giving an input colored image, this procedure is capable of direct regressing of the body, hands, and face in an SMPL-X format, which is not an easy task due to the lack of training data, especially for the previously "unseen" poses, and due to the high dimensionality of the human body. It appears that they solved this problem by extending the SMPL neural-network regressors to the more expressive SMPL-X. However, some shortcomings needed handling, given that SMPL-X is of higher dimensionality of SMLP, thus increasing the overall computational cost and complexity of constructing the model. The other problem was that SMPL-X training data is usually obtained in a controlled environment (indoors), so it lacked the variety provided by in-the-wild datasets. This predicament was fixed by creating a new dataset, employing several datasets containing in-the-wild images, applying SMPLify-X on them, checking, and dropping corrupted automatically generated annotations manually. The third problem with estimating hands and face is that the images are typically downscaled before being feed to the neural networking meaning that in comparison to the full-body, the face and hands will only occupy a small region of the overall image, which will not be enough to get an accurate estimate of them. The transition to the new dataset gives a good estimation for the entire body in general, with proper localization for the hands and face as a starting point. Then they focus the network back on the original scale image for the face and hands to retrieve high-resolution information for these regions and feed this to a dedicated refinement module. These modules act as an expressivity boost by distilling part-specific knowledge from high-quality datasets containing either hand-only or face-only images/data. Finally, the independent components are fine-tuned jointly in an end-to-end manner. Therefore Expose is supposed to estimate more expressive 3D human models with greater precision than pre-existing models such as SMPLify-X, with a drastic decrease in compu-

tational time. However, some might argue that the methodology used to acquire the training data for ExPose model might produce biased results, particularly since incorrect pose annotations produced by the SMPLify-X model were dropped manually instead of being corrected or refined. This action may lead the ExPose model to inherit some of the shortcomings/weaknesses of its predecessor SMPLify-X. It can also use the initial body mesh prediction to define the areas of attention for hands and face specific processing networks. A similar practice is used by OpenPose, where arm keypoints are used to estimate hand bounding boxes in a heuristic manner.

Experiments Result with Examples

Figure 2.17: ExPose results for a right side view exercise routine

Figure 2.18: ExPose results for a simple motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.19: ExPose results for a semi-complex motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.20: ExPose results for a semi-complex motion lying down exercise routine

The results from Smplify-x were not that bad. However, the results from Expose are even better, both quantitatively and qualitatively, as it is shown in the figures [2.17, 2.18, 2.19], even when it comes to the hands and feet making it more favorable than the others. Only the last exercise shown in figure 2.20 have lousy quality, but that is no surprise for us.

A Monocular 3D Whole-Body Pose Estimation System via Regression and Integration Franckmocap

[50, 51] This approach is also SMPL/SMPL-X based and attempts to produce 3D estimation for the entire body, including the face and hands. By running 3D pose regression methods for each body part independently and combining them

with model integration, the final model will result from stitching techniques, so some deformations and irregularities near the joints might appear. They also claim that their latest model outperforms other optimization-based and end-to-end-based methods. Giving an input image, the model estimates the 3D poses of the face, hands independently, and the rest of the body in the form of SMPL-X model, where a separate 3D pose regressor model is responsible for producing the outputs by training it on a dataset related to that body part. Thus effectively dealing with the lack of data by separating each body part and handling them as independent entities. The final step is to combine their output through the integration methods they developed, namely copy-paste, wrist integration network, and an optimization-based method. The copy and paste and wrist integration modules are suitable for time-sensitive or real-time applications, while the optimization-based module is suitable for offline operations requiring higher precision. Therefore the biggest drawback of this method is that the combined assets could contain inconsistent elements stitched together, resulting in an unrealistic looking model, primarily where the stitching is performed (near the hands, legs, and face/neck), hence the name! "FrankMocap" is an homage to Frankenstein's monster in the modern Prometheus according to them.

Experiments Result with Examples

Figure 2.21: FrankMocap results for a right side view exercise routine

Figure 2.22: FrankMocap results for a simple motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.23: FrankMocap results for a semi-complex motion for a front view exercise routine with an approximately 45-degree angle

Figure 2.24: FrankMocap results for a semi-complex motion lying down exercise routine

For the FrankMocap with SMPL-X body models, the results for the body are of good accuracy. However, the feet and hands representations are pretty poor, and the joints that connect the body with the feet and hands result from stitching techniques. Thus, they appear to be deformed in general and incorrect in all [2.21, 2.23, 2.24] of the exercises except for the second one shown in figure 2.22 where the precision is relatively acceptable but low compared to other models claimed in their paper. Even With the better joint integration approaches they have suggested, it is still of lower accuracy than those presented in ExPose, which means that this model will not work for our case.

GHUM/GHUML

[46] Introducing two models. One is more accurate, while the other is a lighter version of a similar model, so there is an accuracy and memory/speed trade-off. The models can also simultaneously predict high-resolution 3D human shapes for the body, hands, and face. More accurate expressions can be captured with additional zooming on the hands and faces. The model’s parameters were trained using variational autoencoders, pose-space deformation correctives, skeleton joint center predictors, and blend skinning functions in a single consistent end-to-end learning loop. They also introduced a 3D dynamic database of over 60 thousand human scans in different configurations and poses/positions. These models can support the body and complex facial expressions and hands details. In contrast to other models, such as in the case of FrancMocap, this model has been built in a manner where the body elements are not predicted in isolation. Thus unlike this model, they could not take advantage of the large-scale data analysis and model construction methodology that newly appeared in the context of deep learning. Several recent full-body models like Adam, Frank, or SMPLify-X, combine legacy components for face, body, and hands but usually focus on constructing a consistent, joint parameterization with proper scaling on top of already learned components, rather than on training a full-body model, end-to-end, based on a large data repository. This approach makes it difficult to take full advantage of the structure in all data simultaneously, experiment with alternative representations for components or other losses, assess end impact, and innovate. However, this particular model follows the principles of end-to-end development pipelines and employs a loss function to be optimized by deep learning methods and neural networks, meaning that it can simultaneously train all com-

ponents body, hands, face, and legs. These models are trained with high-resolution full-body scans and close-up images of hands and faces during movement to capture the most details, ensuring the consistency of the structure in the process. Although there is much merit to these models, the biggest drawback is that deep learning is a data driving approach meaning it will cost a lot to obtain and train the dataset. In contrast, other models might separate body parts and treat them independently to the used different dataset for each part, increasing the amount of training data they can acquire, with that in mind that the authors of the paper do not permit the usage of these two models outside the scope of research projects. Therefore, even though it seems superior to other 3D modeling techniques, we cannot effectively utilize this method.

Adam

[45] Like the other volume-based models, it should be capable of capturing body movements, facial expressions, and hand gestures. It follows the "Frank" model methodology by stitching individual models together to get the complete 3D Human shape. They also introduced a new dataset of humans and optimized the previous Frank model to get what is known as the Adam model. a calibrated model that shares the same skeleton hierarchy as the initial Frank model with a simpler parameterization. These models for total motion capture can be used for motion tracking in a multiview setup where more than a single image can be utilized. For example, stitching different body parts templates into a single skeleton by building on existing keypoint detection for individual body parts, face, bodies, and hands in multiview settings to obtain 3D landmarks for multiple people in one scene. It works in a manner resembling bottom-up approaches. First, they started by using the Frank model as a base and learned a new deformation model called Adam, which should capture different hair and cloth with simplified parameters. The frank model leverages existing models for the body, such as SMLP and different face and hands models. It operates under the assumption that each model captures the relative shape and expected motion details at the appropriate scale for their respective body parts. However, there is a trade-off between images resolution and the field of view for available datasets based on 3D scans. By effectively utilizing different models for the face and hands, their accuracy and shape are increased and seem to have a meaningful visual appearance. However, the problem here is that the model is out-

dated and does not compete with the same state-of-the-art models compared in the paper anymore. Also, even though it improves the overall body and head appearance, it is of no use to us, as this approach will only increase the computational complexity of the model to improve the appearance a little.

Human Mesh Recovery (HMR)

[52] HMR is end-to-end adversarial learning of human pose and shape, capable of reconstructing full-body 3D meshes from a single image. It is built based on SMPL, given that it parameterizes the mesh by 3D joint angles and low-dimensional linear shape space. Indifference to other methods that heavily rely on the 3D joint locations. This approach outputs the relative 3D rotation matrices for each one of the joints in the skeleton. Effectively capturing limbs orientation and heads information alongside the joint landmarks. The rotation ensures that the limbs are of a valid length and keeps symmetricity in check. This approach is applied because they believe that the joints are not sufficient to give a complete detailed representation, given that they are sparse, whereas a surface defines the human body in the 3D space. There is no need to separate the joint angles manually as the models learn to deal with them implicitly. Unfortunately, such an end-to-end approach suffers from some bottlenecks. The first one that is common in all 3D pose estimation models is the lack of training data, especially in comparison to the 2D pose estimation models, and given the fact that 3D annotations are usually obtained in a controlled environment and do not generalize well for in-the-wild images. Since 2D data is mainly available, it is possible to map the 2D-to-3D landmarks. However, this mapping system suffers from a factor of ambiguity. Their approach is supposed to deal with both challenges by using large-scale in-the-wild images for 2D annotated landmarks combined with one of the available large-scale datasets of 3D meshes displaying individuals with pose and shapes variations. Their essential contribution is to utilize the unpaired 2D landmarks along with the 3D scans in a conditional generative adversarial manner. Given an input RGB image, the model attempts to match the 3D Mesh parameters with the 2D camera view in such a way that the 3D keypoints match the annotated 2D keypoints after projection. This approach was carried out to deal with ambiguities, and a discriminator network is employed to determine if the 3D parameters correspond to bodies of real humans or not. Therefore, the discriminator acts as a weak supervisor, and the network tends to output parameters that correspond to

the human body. The network implicitly learns the angle boundaries for each joint and is prevented from outputting deformations. Regardless, this approach has not been refined in a while, meaning that it cannot keep up with the new state-of-the-art models. Therefore we will only be using it as a reference.

2.2 Results

In the end, each of these models has its advantages and disadvantages; we were able to rule out many of them just by examining the results presented in the papers. However, most of them pick and choose the data to display their results and then compare them to other methods, which means that these results are more likely to be biased and subject to criticism. Furthermore, some HPE algorithms that we reviewed are also optimized for in-the-wild dataset scenarios, which does not suit our case, as we seek to optimize for indoor environments. Therefore we qualitatively compared some of them for differently selected videos from our dataset using different settings as well, to find what is visually/qualitatively "better" in general and what is the "best" one for our case, where we need the legs and feet to be fully captured in a controlled environment for a relatively slow movement exercise. We also do not care much about the hands and face for the time being; however, we can still use them in the future.

With that being said, from the results displayed in the figures and other experiments, it is evident that MeTRAbs and MediaPipe's results are of sufficient accuracy for the skeleton-based models, with MediaPipe being faster, which is more suitable for real-time applications; therefore, we will use it as the default model. On the other hand, in the case of the volumetric-based meshes, Expose seems to produce the best results even without providing it with the landmarks obtained from OpenPose for optimization purposes. So we will also use it to construct the expert's avatar and perhaps for future visually based error comparison.

We can also hypothesize that if the placement is correct, then changing the pose estimation algorithm only plays a minor role, given that most of them yield relatively good results on well-placed exercise routines.

Chapter 3

Exercise Position Optimization

As discussed earlier, HPE methods suffer from three crucial bottlenecks and shortcomings. (I) First, the lack of training data regarding 3D pose estimation and the ambiguity left by upscaling 2D-to-3D reference points. (II) Second, The imprecision of mere depth estimation methods utilized by these technologies where the absolute depth from the camera to the subject can be inaccurate, but the relative depth between the person's body points could be approximated efficiently. Nonetheless, the depth estimation heavily depends on the distance from the object to the camera, meaning that knowing the distance beforehand will help to correct these estimations with a lesser margin of error as a postprocessing step. (III) Third, the ambiguity presented by occluded body parts can come from either the surrounding environment where other objects can get in the camera's field of view or the more problematic situation where the subject's body parts can block other vital parts from the camera's standpoint. This issue could be solved by maximizing the visibility of the critical landmarks from each individual's exercise viewpoint, using more than one camera, or perhaps a combination of both techniques could yield the best results.

Our task is to design a customized solution to minimize the effects of these three dilemmas in a way that suits our circumstances and the dataset we are working on, which means that we should tailor the solution in the case of physical rehabilitation exercise (in general) where the environment is controlled to a large extent. The exercise speed is relatively slow, and the most important and most challenging constraint to accomplish, that the accuracy of the model should be superior, unlike any other results, giving the importance of this task and the dangers incorrect estima-

tions could cause to the participants. There are several methods to deal with these weaknesses. All of them revolve around knowing the exact location of the exercise beforehand.

3.1 Overcoming HPE Bottlenecks

For the first obstacle, dealing with the lack of data is no easy task; it is better to conduct an extensive review of HPE algorithms and select the most suitable one after a thorough testing phase. Then, for the second and third obstacles, there comes the need to place the camera and the patient in a way where both constraints are satisfied, meaning the camera to subject distance is pre-determined based on heuristic results. Then, the camera's view field should be able to capture the entire human body, and finally, optimize the relative orientation and angle between the camera and the subject in a manner where critical body parts (joints and limbs) for each particular exercise routine are maximized in terms of visibility throughout the execution of the exercise. To accomplish this outcome, we utilized a pipeline that works in the following manner:

- Pose Estimation Extraction: utilize a skeleton/volumetric HPE method to extract landmarks/avatars for the instructor while performing the exercise routine to be regarded as a reference.
- Semantic Map Construction: A semantic representation of the environment can be accomplished by utilizing a depth camera and specialized software or a replacement by a simulated environment that can provide the same properties.
- Preference Map Construction: Then construct something we will refer to as a preference map, where each exercise's preference map contains the needed information to position the camera and patient in the environment with the appropriate distance and angle.
- Exercise Maximum Bounding Box Calculation: retrieving the maximum width, depth, height for the exercise boundaries and instructor's parameters during the preference map creation process.

- Exercise Position Optimization: localizing and optimizing the exercise location regarding the patient's parameters, the information from the preference map, and a top-down view of the environment using a preconstructed semantic map.
- Visual Path Guide: If any location was found, guide the patient to that location to perform the exercise using visual instructions.
- NLP Textual Instructions: Issue natural language generated commands (using text) to guide the patient to the exercise location based on the environment landmarks, optimize the localization, and finally, exercise correction process is possible.
- Exercise routine Comparison & Evaluation: Apply machine learning, deep learning, and sequence alignment algorithms to detect errors in the patient's exercise compared to the correct pattern performed by the instructor.
- Exercise routine Correction: This can be done by either visual instruction to display the out of alignment parts or simple text commands to fix the situation in a real-time online manner.
- Exercise Routine Repetition Counter: Count the number of correct iterations the patient performs.

3.1.1 Pose Estimation Extraction

The first step is to extract the expert's avatar, and there is the need to utilize a skeleton or a volumetric pose estimation algorithm such as OpenPose or Expose on the exercise performed by the therapist/expert, which we will refer to as "corrector or reference exercise." This step aims to develop the technology independently of the selected algorithms to be switched out with ease depending on the development of new technologies. The output of this process is a sequence of 3D models/objects/meshes of the pose estimation algorithm for each frame in the input video. Also, depending on the used algorithm, the volumetric mesh size could exceed 1 MB, which might be problematic in the long run for lengthy exercises. However, a shape/size trade-off could solve this issue.

3.1.2 Semantic Map Construction

One of the project's technologies that it will depend on is environment semantic mapping by utilizing Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) techniques. The agent could gain knowledge of its latest position and discovers a new environment. Information to facilitate automatic reasoning can be acquired from the environment task execution. Eventually, it can establish beneficial human-machine collaboration. First, the 3D semantic representation of the world can be generated in real-time or offline for greater accuracy. Then, mapping 3D objects, including the avatar, from the real world onto the 2D image plane. These steps include Spatial Perception, Feature/Keypoint Extraction, 3D Reconstruction, and semantic segmentation in that order. Objects will be detected at the end of the semantic segmentation and assigned pixel-wise labels. However, precise detection of the object's size, shape, relative position, and attributes call for the camera's intrinsic parameters. This step is essential to interact with objects and avoid obstacles autonomously, especially when applying the guiding system to find the shortest path.

A semantic representation of the environment can be accomplished by utilizing a depth camera and specialized software, such as in [53], where they utilize a system for sharing and reusing 3D semantic information between multiple agents with variant viewpoints and creating a 3D dense semantic model of the space from human viewpoints. Geometric reconstruction can be created sparsely with detachable or densely connected sensors such as RGB or RGB-depth cameras for precious calculation or inaccurately using depth estimation techniques giving the camera parameters. Semantic class estimations are done using a pre-trained model on 2D RGB images, which could be back-projected onto the reconstructed geometry. Thus effectively labeling independent voxels within the environment with the appropriate labels. Although only the occupancy map is required, the semantic information could be used for the guiding system. Also, replacing the 2D semantic segmentation model with a more sophisticated 3D model could remove the need for depth estimates. However, achieving such a high-accuracy model seems to be a tall order in the near future, at least.

Given that we are using a vision-based system indoors, visual SLAM methods come to mind. This approach is based on sparse feature maps as preferred in this scenario. Consequently, one of the most popular methods for indoor SLAM is re-

lated to ORB methods introduced in [54]. The next step is to use a reconstruction method. A real-time algorithm should be used if the application requires online reconstruction. Such methods can represent and store the model in a point cloud format, which is straightforward to handle. Considering any 2D semantic segmentation method that predicts pixel-wise semantic class labels for the input RGB or RGBD frame and register the segmentation masks on the input depth channel of the depth sensor, where an accuracy-speed trade-off could take effect. The reconstruction module first generates a textured semantically labeled point cloud per frame by projecting depth values of the image with a known camera model and known pose to the 3D space. Then integrate these per-frame point clouds into a Truncated Signed Distance Field (TSDF) volume where TSDF is a 3D voxel matrix describing entities within a volume of space labeled with each voxel the same label according to the distance from the closest surface within the space. The result is a point cloud that semantically represents the environment, addressing actual dimensions and distance to the nearest approximation.

Downscaling the 3D point cloud into 2D by effectively eliminating the height dimension, we can obtain a map-like representation of the environment that is easier and a lot more efficient to deal with in most cases.

Simulation

In order to facilitate the development of the methods in parallel simulated environments are used as an intermediate medium. Since most simulators provide a preconstructed environment with capabilities similar to those in Robot Operating Systems (ROS), then they are helpful in such a situation. Yet, without additional hardware-related complexity. The environment provides semantic information and a standard display for the user, such as in the case of Habitat [55, 56]. Therefore, we will utilize it to test multiple environments without the need for hardware complexity.

3.1.3 Preference Map Construction

The next step is to utilize the previously constructed expert avatar to generate synthesized data to be used in the construction process of data structure we will refer to as a preference map. Each exercise's preference map contains the needed

information to position the camera and patient in the environment, such as distance range between the camera and the subject, most optimal angle and orientation between the camera and the subject, also possibly the optimal camera height if required (it could only work if the camera had an adjustable stand). The synthesized data is created by rotating the avatar in different directions along the vertical axis and potentially shifting the avatar along the vertical axis to determine the best height to place the camera at with the best avatar rotation with respect to the camera's field view as well. The optimal rotation, distance, and height assessment are done by a scoring function considering the visibility of vital joints and limbs given a particular exercise for all frames in the video or all phases of the exercise in question. Thus, effectively encode the required information into the preference map to be used in later steps.

3.1.4 Exercise Maximum Bounding Box Calculation

The camera's parameters, such as the focal length, the maximum width, depth, height for the exercise boundaries, and instructor's parameters, can be evaluated accurately from the exercise skeleton or avatar. Also, establishing the maximum exercise boundaries can be done by considering the maximum possible stretching of body parts along the three axes horizontal, vertical, and depth, x , y , z , respectively.

3.1.5 Exercise Position Optimization

By effectively utilizing and combining the information retrieved from the previous steps alongside a top-down view of the environment using a preconstructed semantic map will yield what we will refer to as the optimal exercise location, and it is accomplishable through the following steps:

- Lowering the dimensionality of the constructed semantic map from 3D to 2D by disregarding the height parameter assuming that no objects are hanging from the ceiling could endanger the exercise execution protocol (less than approximately two meters). Therefore, the created top-down view of the environment will serve as an occupancy map.
- The top-down view of the environment can be searched entirely by shifting the exercise boundaries a pre-determined number of strides along the vertical and

horizontal axis, attempting to fit the bounding box in the environment using different rotations without clashing with other objects/obstacles.

- Upon acquiring a suitable position to place the patient in, the free region around it is calculated, and the position with the maximum free region surrounding it is considered the optimal position to place the exercise. After that, considering the information obtained in the preference map, a suitable position to place the camera needs to be found regarding these constraints. The distance range from the patient, the angle between camera and patient, and optionally the camera's height (if the camera had an adjustable stand).
- After selecting the camera position, the camera's field view is checked for obstacles to ensure that nothing is blocking the camera's view to the patient.
- Suppose there was no suitable position to place the camera where the constraints from the preference map are satisfied (distance and angle). Then the operation is repeated from the second step until the system finds the most appropriate location to perform that particular exercise.

3.2 Path Instructions and Avatar Placement

3.2.1 Visual Path Guide

There are two methods to display the information required for the patient to find the exercise position. The simplest one is by visualizing the directions in phases on the top-down view of the occupancy map and letting the patient make sense of it using their cognitive abilities. However, when the patient positions the camera, they cannot accurately determine where they should locate themselves and their orientation. Instead, they could only estimate it from what they have previously seen, eventually leading the patient to deviate from the original optimal position, even by a little, which might degrade the quality of the pose estimation a bit.

3.2.2 NLP Guide Textual Instructions

The other approach is by issuing natural language-related instructions using text or voice. This approach is much more complex to complete correctly than the visual

method. However, when the patient sets the camera down, they can still receive the instruction verbally (text-to-speech). A simple rule-based system is employed to guide the patient towards the target by utilizing the semantic information of the environment, and also measuring the distance between the next step location and the closest tangible object, considering the object's room, the distance to the target, and the patient/camera field of view in the current step. Furthermore, these instructions could be issued automatically by utilizing this information for each step. When the direction of movement changes, then a new step takes effect.

There are two other places such a simple rule-based system could help, in the first case while establishing the patient position in the environment after placing the camera. Also, exercise correction instructions could be issued in real-time to get the patient back on track after deviation from the exercise. However, they are beyond the scope of the thesis.

3.2.3 Avatar Placement

The final step is to position the avatar previously extracted from the instructor where the exercise is set for execution by the patient. Therefore effectively visualizing the process to the user and working in a place of visual instructions. By adding each mesh that represents a frame at a point of time to the scene, then reverting the scene to its previous state before adding the mesh, then adding the next mesh will give the illusion that the frames are moving forward in time. First, of course, some adjustment for the frame rate to match the real-time is in order. Most cameras have a Frame Per Second (FPS) ratio of 30. therefore this number needs to be matched. Otherwise, some jitter might take effect.

3.2.4 Experiments Result with Examples

Visual Path Instructions

Figure 3.1: Example of visual instructions for short path planning and guidance for the semi-complex exercise routine

Figure 3.2: Example of visual instructions for long path planning and guidance for the semi-complex exercise routine

Figure 3.3: Volumetric avatar placement in the selected position for the semi-complex exercise routine

Figure 3.4: Example of visual instructions for short path planning and guidance for the semi-complex lying down exercise routine

Figure 3.6: Volumetric avatar placement in the selected position for the semi-complex lying down exercise routine

Figure 3.7: The optimal position for the semi-complex lying down exercise routine in different rooms/environments

In the [3.1, 3.2] and [3.4, 3.5] figures for the first and second exercises, respectively, the task is to find and display the path from any given feasible position in the map to the exercise location and place the camera in the suitable position afterwards. Each example contains a topdown view of the environment for each step with the visual instructions and images representing the current scene from the camera's point of view as indicated on the map. The subject is expected to follow them to reach the required position to start the exercise routine. For example, in 3.3 and 3.6, the optimal position is visualized as the maximum bounding box boundaries for a particular exercise in green, and the camera is shown in cyan, with the black parallel line indicating the camera's field of view, they are used to ensure that

no objects are between the camera and the participant while locating the optimal position. By placing the camera and the subject in the corresponding locations, the exercise can be visualized for the patient so that they can mimic it under the same settings. Although the exercise shown in figure 3.3 seems to have decent accuracy, the avatar landmarks were visible when constructing the avatar. Unfortunately, the same cannot be said about the exercise representation shown in the figure 3.6, where the landmarks were not detected correctly due to incorrect placement for the camera resulting in a relatively poor avatar in comparison with good placements. However, the system will still try to make up for these shortcomings by adjusting the angle for the subject while constructing the preference map. Finally, The last figure of this section 3.7 displays the possible placement strategy in different environments.

Written Path Instructions

Figure 3.8: Visual and textual natural language-based generated instructions for guidance between two random navigable points in the environment

The natural language instructions can be shown in figure 3.8, where the landmarks in the environment are utilized along with the semantic information from the camera to guide the person using automatically generated commands by a rule-based system, which seems to be sufficient if the information is indeed correct. Furthermore, by grouping objects based on where they should be located in a regular household, the map can be divided into regions, thus effectively helping in giving instructions from a third person's perspective, as shown in the figure.

Chapter 4

Exercises Error Detection

4.1 Exercise Routine Comparison & Evaluation

It is the most crucial and error-prone step in the entire process, and all the steps we have taken so far are mere preparation for this phase. We will try different techniques ranging from machine learning, deep learning, and sequence alignment algorithms to detect errors in the patient's exercise compared to the correct pattern performed by the instructor. All of them will utilize the extracted HPE in one way or another. To find the most suitable method for our applications and other domains, a comprehensive review of the feasible technologies is required as this area is still underdeveloped, and not all opportunities have been explored for the time being. Accordingly, new and novel approaches are needed to adapt to the high accuracy requirements under data and computational capacity restraints.

4.2 Learning-Based Approaches

With a dataset of videos for individuals performing the same exercise from different angles and distances in different environments (not necessarily needed the same room might be sufficient depending on the approach), it is possible to utilize this data in a machine learning or deep learning algorithm to establish a model capable of detecting error patterns in the exercise. However, such an approach has two shortcomings. (I) the lack of available data, our dataset does comprise of many exercises. However, we assume that the instructor must perform each exercise only once or twice if needed, which means there are only one to two videos per exercise for the

same expert. Needless to say, this is insufficient for any learning-based algorithm. Therefore, some methods could be utilized to automatically generate the required training data instead of throwing the towel. Assuming the instructor's volumetric-based representation or avatar while "flawlessly" performing the exercise has been acquired. This type of approach is employed to synthesize more training data by performing a series of randomly generated transformation operations such as rotation, translation, and scaling on the avatar. The second step is to manually acquire the dataset from the generated images or keep it all, depending on the algorithm and the use case. Finally, the selected dataset is fed to an HPE algorithm, and the resulting landmarks are treated as a sequence of time-series datasets and then passed into the appropriate machine learning algorithm.

4.2.1 Checkpoints Classification Based Approach

In this method, specifying a set of "checkpoints" for each exercise is a mandatory requirement, the minimal set of checkpoints is the set of terminal states (beginning and end). Any new set should extend these two default points because we consider each checkpoint a crucial turning point in the exercise execution phase where a significant deviation occurs, as illustrated in the figures. While extracting the dataset, these checkpoints need to be labeled manually, and each algorithm tends to handle them differently, although the general concept is similar. The checkpoints are considered as training data. Therefore, the frames from the subject's exercise are the input after applying the same HPE algorithm used for the training. The task is to determine which checkpoint a frame belongs to (classify) and determine that the exercise flows correctly from the first checkpoint, known as the starting point, until the last checkpoint, known as the endpoint. There are different methods to measure the similarity between a set of point clouds. In fact, We can consider this task to be a simple classification problem. First, however, we will try the basic nearest-neighbor-based approach and generalize it to other algorithms. If a checkpoint is missing, then the assumption is that the patient did not perform the exercise correctly, and the error bound is between the two checkpoints surrounding the missing phase.

These methods can be considered a "weak-supervisor" where deviation from the optimal exercise is possible as long as the patient goes through all checkpoints. Furthermore, therefore might not be appropriate for our purposes unless many check-

points are defined, leading to some confusion and misclassifications, especially if the checkpoints happen to be close to each other. Perhaps the flaw makes them more suitable as a regular exercise counter for non-complex movements or in HAR, where the activity comprises main steps to be taken in order or orderless.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Approach

KNN is a fundamental traditional machine learning algorithm known for its simplicity and efficiency for small datasets. Therefore, it is suitable for a first choice when little to no knowledge of the data distribution [57]. One of the many advantages of KNN is that it requires no preprocessing of the labeled dataset before using them. The crisp nearest-neighbor classification rule assigns an input sample vector of unknown classification to the class of its nearest neighbor [58], hence the name. Extending the idea to k-nearest neighbors is possible by assigning the input vector to the dominant class among k-nearest neighbors. When more than one neighbor is under consideration, it is possible to have a tie between them. Therefore it is recommended to have k set to an odd number [59]. The training/fitting process for this approach is pretty basic. First, the algorithm stores the training data and determines the nearest neighbor to each new test/prediction data element by matching the input vector with the information acquired during training using distance measurement, with the Eculdien distance being the most common measurement to use. Furthermore, assign the closest label to each element based on the majority votes of the dominant class. Therefore, by considering the KNN approach, it is possible to feed the entire training dataset to the model, predict the closest neighbors to each input vector independently and assign the appropriate class/checkpoint for each input. While this process is done, at the same time, it checks if the phase is in order and no checkpoints have been skipped. A repetition counter can be implemented by calculating the number of perfectly completed iterations. It is set only to accept successful exercise repetitions, where no checkpoints are skipped. Some sanity check is required to restrict the minimum number of label occurrences for the phase to be considered complete, which depends on the number of frames fed to the system, with 30 FPS being the default. However, real-time performance could be achieved around 15-20 FPS without compromising the integrity of the method.

4.3 Sequence Approach

This approach is quite similar to the time series approach as the input for this method is a time series of the landmarks for a giving exercise. It is also similar to the classification approach in the training data creation process with simple additions, by randomly increasing the sequence size by either increasing the number of frames or duplicating some of the frames, or decreasing the sequence length by removing frames. Anything goes as long as it removes the exercise execution length bias from the dataset. The most suitable architectures for this approach are recurrent neural network (RNN) based models such as Long-Short Term Memory LSTM and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), especially given that they have been extensively researched in human activity recognition. However, this method is highly data-driven, and without a large amount of data, it is unlikely to yield good results.

4.4 Time Series Analysis Approaches

Before starting with this family of methods, we first need to ensure that the obtained input landmarks sequence from the patient's HPE landmarks and the obtained pattern landmarks sequence from the expert's HPE are aligned correctly, which means that both sequences should be from the same or have a relatively similar viewpoint. Then, depending on the distance from the camera and the subject's width and height, there might be a need to rescale one of the skeletons to fit the other. This takes us back to the purpose of the first part of the project, which is to locate the optimal position to perform the exercise concerning the camera angle, distance, and placement. If the patient followed the instruction, then the HPE for the subject should be close to the expert's pattern. After that, the two skeletons will only reach the final alignment after applying cloud point alignment methods to match the input skeleton with the expert's pattern. Finally, after the two skeletons have been aligned nearly perfectly, there comes the need to apply time series-based methods to check the sequence of skeleton alignments.

4.4.1 Dynamic Time Warping (DTW)

DTW is a well-known classical approach developed for use in many areas. It was first explored for speech recognition purposes as it can cope with different speaking

speeds. As the years passed, the application potential increased with handwritten and gesture matching, sign language recognition, gesture recognition, and many more. The method is highly efficient as the time-series similarity measurement minimizes the effects of shifting and distortion in time by allowing the "elastic" transformation of the time series to detect similar shapes with different phases. Given two time series, DTW yields an optimal solution in $O(MN)$ time, Where M is the first sequence and N is the second sequence. [60] by calculating what it refers to as the optimal match between two sequences. The optimal match has to satisfy all the restrictions and rules and has a minimal cost; the cost is computed as the sum of absolute differences between their values for each matched pair of indices. In simpler terms, the algorithm's main purpose is to measure the similarity between two temporal sequences with different length. For instance, In our application, we must measure similarities during the execution of a particular exercise that could be detected using DTW, even if the two individuals do not have the same execution rate.

However, it could be considered too sensitive to distortion, especially in the time axis as the sequence moves further in time [61], which means longer sequences are more likely to yield higher error rate even if the similarity between them does not shift by much.

4.5 Distance with Window Selection

This technique might seem to be no more than a naive approach at first glance. Nonetheless, selectively finding windows where the distance between the input landmarks from the subject to the target landmarks obtained from the expert's exercise execution might prove superior to the previously discussed alignment methods and also computationally efficient as it only requires one pass over the minimum sequence length plus frame dropping time, with additional costs for the window comparison and selection time depending on the algorithm. Assuming that the subject's sequence length or the number of frames is most likely to be more or less than the number of frames in the expert's sequence, then there comes the need to "normalize" the two sequences by either adding/repeating frames in the shorter sequence or removing frames from the more extended sequence. Since shorter sequences will have faster execution time, and longer ones will increase the number of possible duplicates, tak-

ing the second approach by dropping some of the frames in the longer sequences seems more feasible. A simple method to solve this problem is to downsample the long sequence by selectively dropping some of the frames. i.e., drop every sample at a constant rate of $\text{Every } \text{int}(M/N)$ where M and N are the length of the long and short sequences, respectively. Another method could be done by moving a window over the extended sequence and matching each element in that window with the corresponding element in the short sequence, then keeping the element that yields the highest similarity in the window.

4.6 Exercise Routine Repetition Counter

Counting the number of iterations the patient performs. Some algorithms could clearly define and start and stop points for each exercise, such as in the case of the checkpoints-based approach, effectively counting the number of iterations, whereas other tasks are not as simple as in the case of sequence-based approaches.

4.7 Exercises Correction

Detecting errors on its own is only a prerequisite for the correction step, to achieve this, more details are required, and it depends on the algorithm used for error detection, meaning that each one may give a different outcome analyzing these results in comparison with the correct exercise routine will give rise to some deviations. We will call these deviations that are above specific threshold errors.

4.7.1 Feature Engineering

Although detecting the deviation between sequences of landmarks is sufficient to know that an error has occurred. However, in order to get more details about the error and how it deviates from the correct reference sequence, new features need to be defined. For instance, the angle between specific joints can determine the difference between the correct exercise and the patient's imitation of particular limbs.

4.8 Results and Observations

In This section we categorized and reviewed some methods to detect potential errors in the patient’s exercise routine. Although some of these methods do not exist in the related literature, they are ideas tested during the thesis’s implementation phase. The learning-based approaches that utilize machine learning and deep learning are popular in the HAR system. However, utilizing volumetric-based human body models to generate data automatically is new in this field, to the best of our knowledge. The time series approaches were also developed and tested on the dataset. However, the sequence-based approach was dropped due to the complexity of the method and relatively low accuracy and confidence in the obtained results, as it seems not to be suitable for high accuracy medical rehabilitation.

In the figure shown below 4.1 we illustrate the classification steps of a two-phase/checkpoints KNN based approach with a repetition counter for a simple exercise.

Although these methods have already been developed, extensive testing to find the most capable one is still ongoing.

Figure 4.1: Example of using KNN approach for two-phase checkpoint classification approach

Chapter 5

Additional Refinements

5.1 Image Enhancement Techniques

There is an additional factor to consider that could become a potential bottleneck in the pose estimation process in case of the human pose is not well estimated due to some environmental settings, which might cause some missing landmarks. Then depending on the environment, the lighting condition might not be good enough to obtain a fair quality skeleton. For example, if the frames were too bright, the edges might not be precise, and the same goes for dark rooms, which might force the HPE to go off the grid and then attempt to estimate the missing landmarks according to default or heuristics, which is a behavior that we do not desire. Therefore, it is essential first to recognize such a condition and then attempt to avoid or fix it if possible. This task could be accomplished by modifying the quality of the frames before feeding them into the HPE algorithm and effectively fixing the issue. Nonetheless, when such a situation occurs, it is appropriate to warn the subject of the situation. Then, if the patient could fix the lighting condition or whatever is causing the problem, the issue could be avoided altogether, thus saving precious computational resources. However, additional digital image pre-processing sequences might be required if the issue cannot be avoided. Image enhancement techniques are typically objective, meaning the quality of the resulting image highly depends on the observer's opinion. Therefore, it is essential to attempt and optimize the parameters by applying a range of different values to the image enhancement methods and feeding them to the HPE algorithm, thus effectively shifting the role of the observer to the algorithm itself and determining the best parameters based on joints and limbs

detection visibility and confidence. We will consider some techniques and situations requiring such image enhancement techniques.

5.1.1 Brightness and Contrast Adjustments

An Image processor is a function capable of taking at least one image to produce and output a processed image. According to [62], image transformations are categorized into two distinct classes as either Neighborhood (area-based) operators or Point operators (pixel transforms), where each input pixel can only impact the value of the corresponding output pixel with regards to some globally defined parameters that operate the same way for all pixels. Brightness and contrast adjustments are good examples of such operators and color correction and transformations. So to apply such adjustments to the images, we are required to perform the digital image processing operations on them. We will not go into details as they do not directly interest us. Just the idea of being able to enhance the HPE quality using such techniques is what we are seeking.

5.1.2 Image Sharpening

: In contrast to the previously mentioned application, image sharpening falls under the Neighborhood-based operation, where a carefully selected NxM mask or a kernel is applied iteratively to each Neighborhood in the image. By predefining a selection of kernels, we can apply them to the input stream to determine an average of joints and limbs visibility and compare them to get the most effective kernel or none if the image did not need any enhancement in the first place.

5.1.3 Unsharp Masking

Unsharp masking (UM) suggested by [63] falls under the image sharpening methodology. It first creates a blurred "unsharp" negative image to mask the original image. Then, in order to create an image that is less blurry than the input image, and the unsharp mask is combined with the original positive image. The mask works by reducing the density rate of the original image without significantly affecting the density of individual components. The approach typically starts by applying a gaussian blur to a copy of the original image and then compares it to the original. The images are subtracted if the difference is more significant than a

predefined threshold. Unsharp masking is a flexible and effective way to improve sharpness, especially in scanned images. Generally speaking, UM could be a linear or a nonlinear filter that amplifies the high-frequency components. Nevertheless, unfortunately, it may create unwanted conspicuous edge effects or increase image noise. As with most image processing techniques, the results could be considered user objective. Some adaptive filter-based methods control the contribution of the sharpening path to enhance the contrast in highly detailed areas and neglect areas with no significant changes, such as suggested by [64]. However, for our purpose, the regular version would prove sufficient.

5.1.4 Illumination Adjustment

In order to change the illumination, we need to apply gamma correction, which is considered an irreversible nonlinear operation used to encode and decode luminance values in images. It is essentially employed to optimize the usage of bits by taking advantage of the nonlinear fashion that humans use in order to perceive light and color when encoding an image or bandwidth used to transform an image. Given that the human perception of brightness under standard illumination circumstances where it is not entirely black nor extremely bright follows an approximate power function as stated in [65]

5.1.5 Edge Enhancement

This method depends on image detection techniques and works by magnifying detected edges in a particular image based on the computed edge points as a reference. In addition, this method works by increasing the contrast of the pixels around the specific edges, increasing the visibility of the edges after applying the filter.

5.1.6 Experiments with Results

In the end, numerous techniques could be employed to enhance the image quality as a pre-processing step. However, as is stated before, it is preferred that the environment be more suitable than applying techniques to adjust the quality of the images. Nonetheless, most of the algorithms covered in the section are computationally efficient, and that is why there were taken into consideration, there are plenty

of other methods that might also prove to be fruitful, but we will not expand any further.

Figure 5.1: Examples for image processing results

The figure 5.1 displays some of the examples of these experiments to provide a use case to prove the effectiveness of these methods in certain circumstances. As shown in the figure, sometimes, the room is not well lighted, or the sunlight could cause it to be blindingly bright, consequently casting a shadow on the from the window's side and affecting the quality of the images in the process. If this situation cannot be avoided, then several techniques with several pre-determined parameters will be used in parallel with the pose estimation algorithm to calculate the visibility of the joints under such conditions, thus effectively employing the HPE algorithm as the observer to judge the quality of the resulting images in the methods point of view. The figure displays an example where the left leg is in the body's shadow. Thus the algorithm is not always able to detect it effectively. However, after applying several methods, illumination enhancement, unsharp Masking, and sharpening seem to be able to fix this issue in variant degrees of success.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Future Work

6.1 Future Work

In this section, the missing components needed for a completely functional, highly accurate rehabilitation exercise correction system will be presented with a possible plan, future work, and potential bottlenecks with additional ideas that were not implemented yet.

6.1.1 Exercise Correction

To relate the modifications of potential errors discovered in the patient's exercise routine compared to the expert's seemingly flawless execution of the same exercise is attainable by applying one of two methods, either by (I) visual means such as displaying both skeletons or avatars and then displaying the differences between them, or highlighting the individual parts (limbs and joints) that deviate from the reference exercise routine performed by the therapist. This approach might be a bit tricky. For example, different individuals' scales and distances from the camera will result in diverse skeleton representations and avatars from the size perspective. Nonetheless, it is still a good solution as it avoids the difficulty of the natural language system and its drawbacks, such as the language barrier, instability, and the enormous amount of required training data, making it easy to relay the information to the user a friendly manner. On the other hand, (II) NLP-based instructions could allow real-time human-machine interaction and issuing correction commands instead of the visual method where the subject will have to continuously look at the screen to notice updates or review the exercise report after performing it at least once.

Therefore, perhaps the best possible solution is not one but a combination of both methods to provide a real-time simulation of the expert interaction via verbal commands and provide reports that can be used through time to check the improvement of the patient.

6.1.2 NLP-based Placement Instructions

One of the most significant shortcomings of the current optimal position optimization method is that it heavily relies on occupancy or semantic map of the environment, which requires a set of sensors capable of capturing or measuring the depth as well as the RGB image of the scene. Since such cameras are typically not cost-efficient, there might be another way to perform this step by letting the patient place the camera in a position of their choice and then following a simple set of instructions to place the subject at the correct position by issuing natural language-based commands aimed at establishing the relatively correct distance between the camera and patient and the relative rotation for the both of them.

6.1.3 Multiple Camera Views

One of the most significant shortcomings of the current optimal position optimization method is that it heavily relies on occupancy or semantic map of the environment, which requires a set of sensors capable of capturing or measuring the depth as well as the RGB image of the scene. Since such cameras are typically not cost-efficient, there might be another way to perform this step by letting the patient place the camera in a position of their choice and then following a simple set of instructions to place the subject at the correct position by issuing natural language-based commands aimed at establishing the relatively correct distance between the camera and patient and the relative rotation for the both of them in an interactive online manner.

6.1.4 Generalization to Other Fitness Practices

Since the rehabilitation scenario is more demanding than regular fitness exercise, it is safe to assume that the level of technology achieved so far is generalizable to other applications where the accuracy is not required to be extremely high. This means that it is probable to deploy an AI-powered fitness trainer capable of learning,

distinguishing deviations from the experts' pattern, and counting repetitions from a single video giving a well-positioned camera regarding the angle and distance from the subject. It is also possible to use the same technology in HAR, especially in hazardous situations where a high level of accuracy is needed, such as the case of self-driving cars where the system needs to interact with the static environment and its moving components such as humans and cyclists.

6.2 Conclusion

The thesis is a part of a more influential project with the ultimate vision of automating and supporting the work of rehabilitation therapists, where the starting point is set as a case study for total knee replacement rehabilitation exercises. This goal can be accomplished by interacting with the patient in a vision-related manner or a dialog system capable of issuing and understanding the connection between the execution of exercises sequences. Therefore, in this work, we have extensively researched available HPE algorithms where the skeleton-based or the volumetric-based method has different usage in search of the optimal methods with constraints on accuracy/precision/error-rate. Afterward, we tested and extended a selected few of those methods on the total knee replacement rehabilitation dataset in order to evaluate them qualitatively by examining samples from the provided dataset. The evaluations provided by the papers could be biased and subject to criticism due to some constraints that might be present in the utilized datasets because of the data distribution, format, or other irregularities. The second step would be to overcome some of the unavoidable bottlenecks presented by HPE technology, such as in the case of body parts occlusion and imprecision in the depth estimation provided by such error-prone deep learning models, which are primarily trained on an upsampled 2D-to-3D pose estimation datasets, due to the difficulty of obtaining 3D datasets. The solution that we implemented is based on a pre-defined placement association between the camera's angle and distance from the patient regarding each exercise individually. The camera angle and distance are selected to maximize the joint's visibility score across consecutive frames for each workout. Moreover, supplying visual and textual instructions to reach the optimally chosen position step by step and display the avatar in the selected position to visualize the process for the patient. All of the previous phases are considered a preparatory step for the final section, where

we implemented and tested multiple methods for error detection in the patient's exercise routine compared to the expert's performance. These error mechanisms aim to provide possible correction steps for the patient, whether in real-time as a form of verbal, textual, or visual communication or offline as a form of reports and reviews.

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Bibliography

- [1] Qi Dang et al. “Deep learning based 2d human pose estimation: A survey”. In: *Tsinghua Science and Technology* 24.6 (2019), pp. 663–676.
- [2] Ce Zheng et al. “Deep learning-based human pose estimation: A survey”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2012.13392* (2020).
- [3] João Antunes et al. “AHA-3D: A Labelled Dataset for Senior Fitness Exercise Recognition and Segmentation from 3D Skeletal Data.” In: *BMVC*. 2018, p. 332.
- [4] Xin Jin et al. “Virtual personal trainer via the kinect sensor”. In: *2015 IEEE 16th international conference on communication technology (ICCT)*. IEEE. 2015, pp. 460–463.
- [5] Matthias Seuter et al. “Live-feedback from the imus: Animated 3d visualization for everyday-exercising”. In: *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM International Joint Conference on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing: Adjunct*. 2016, pp. 904–907.
- [6] Bo Zhou et al. “Never skip leg day: A novel wearable approach to monitoring gym leg exercises”. In: *2016 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom)*. IEEE. 2016, pp. 1–9.
- [7] Mihai Fieraru et al. “AIFit: Automatic 3D Human-Interpretable Feedback Models for Fitness Training”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2021, pp. 9919–9928.
- [8] Jianbo Wang et al. “AI coach: Deep human pose estimation and analysis for personalized athletic training assistance”. In: *Proceedings of the 27th ACM International Conference on Multimedia*. 2019, pp. 374–382.

- [9] Haoran Xie, Atsushi Watatani, and Kazunori Miyata. “Visual feedback for core training with 3d human shape and pose”. In: *2019 Nicograph International (NicoInt)*. IEEE. 2019, pp. 49–56.
- [10] Haoran Xie, Atsushi Watatani, and Kazunori Miyata. “CoreUI: Interactive Core Training System with 3D Human Shape”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.09196* (2021).
- [11] Matthew Loper et al. “SMPL: A skinned multi-person linear model”. In: *ACM transactions on graphics (TOG)* 34.6 (2015), pp. 1–16.
- [12] Qingtian Yu et al. “Deep Learning-Enabled Multitask System for Exercise Recognition and Counting”. In: *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction* 5.9 (2021), p. 55.
- [13] Georgia Chalvatzaki et al. “i-Walk Intelligent Assessment System: Activity, Mobility, Intention, Communication”. In: *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer. 2020, pp. 500–517.
- [14] Ying Li et al. “Human pose estimation based in-home lower body rehabilitation system”. In: *2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*. IEEE. 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [15] Alina Miron et al. “IntelliRehabDS (IRDS)—A Dataset of Physical Rehabilitation Movements”. In: *Data* 6.5 (2021), p. 46.
- [16] Murtadha Aldeer, Mehdi Javanmard, and Richard P Martin. “A review of medication adherence monitoring technologies”. In: *Applied System Innovation* 1.2 (2018), p. 14.
- [17] Jan Stenum et al. “Applications of Pose Estimation in Human Health and Performance across the Lifespan”. In: *Sensors* 21.21 (2021), p. 7315.
- [18] Djamila Romaiassa Beddiar et al. “Vision-based human activity recognition: a survey”. In: *Multimedia Tools and Applications* 79.41 (2020), pp. 30509–30555.
- [19] Yan Wang, Shuang Cang, and Hongnian Yu. “A survey on wearable sensor modality centred human activity recognition in health care”. In: *Expert Systems with Applications* 137 (2019), pp. 167–190.
- [20] Oscar D Lara and Miguel A Labrador. “A survey on human activity recognition using wearable sensors”. In: *IEEE communications surveys & tutorials* 15.3 (2012), pp. 1192–1209.

- [21] Jindong Wang et al. “Deep learning for sensor-based activity recognition: A survey”. In: *Pattern Recognition Letters* 119 (2019), pp. 3–11.
- [22] T Subetha and S Chitrakala. “A survey on human activity recognition from videos”. In: *2016 international conference on information communication and embedded systems (ICICES)*. IEEE. 2016, pp. 1–7.
- [23] Shian-Ru Ke et al. “A review on video-based human activity recognition”. In: *Computers* 2.2 (2013), pp. 88–131.
- [24] Sarvesh Vishwakarma and Anupam Agrawal. “A survey on activity recognition and behavior understanding in video surveillance”. In: *The Visual Computer* 29.10 (2013), pp. 983–1009.
- [25] Leonardo Onofri et al. “A survey on using domain and contextual knowledge for human activity recognition in video streams”. In: *Expert Systems with Applications* 63 (2016), pp. 97–111.
- [26] Tej Singh and Dinesh Kumar Vishwakarma. “Human activity recognition in video benchmarks: A survey”. In: *Advances in Signal Processing and Communication*. Springer, 2019, pp. 247–259.
- [27] Yong Du, Wei Wang, and Liang Wang. “Hierarchical recurrent neural network for skeleton based action recognition”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2015, pp. 1110–1118.
- [28] Jun Liu et al. “Global context-aware attention lstm networks for 3d action recognition”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2017, pp. 1647–1656.
- [29] Amir Shahroudy et al. “Ntu rgb+ d: A large scale dataset for 3d human activity analysis”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2016, pp. 1010–1019.
- [30] Sijie Song et al. “An end-to-end spatio-temporal attention model for human action recognition from skeleton data”. In: *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. Vol. 31. 1. 2017.
- [31] Pengfei Zhang et al. “View adaptive recurrent neural networks for high performance human action recognition from skeleton data”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2017, pp. 2117–2126.

- [32] Vivek Veeriah, Naifan Zhuang, and Guo-Jun Qi. “Differential recurrent neural networks for action recognition”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*. 2015, pp. 4041–4049.
- [33] Wentao Zhu et al. “Co-occurrence feature learning for skeleton based action recognition using regularized deep LSTM networks”. In: *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. Vol. 30. 1. 2016.
- [34] Sijie Yan, Yuanjun Xiong, and Dahua Lin. “Spatial temporal graph convolutional networks for skeleton-based action recognition”. In: *Thirty-second AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. 2018.
- [35] Yucheng Chen, Yingli Tian, and Mingyi He. “Monocular human pose estimation: A survey of deep learning-based methods”. In: *Computer Vision and Image Understanding* 192 (2020), p. 102897.
- [36] Valentin Bazarevsky et al. “BlazePose: On-device Real-time Body Pose tracking”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.10204* (2020).
- [37] Ivan Grishchenko and RE Valentin Bazarevsky. “MediaPipe Holistic—Simultaneous Face, Hand and Pose Prediction, on Device”. In: *Retrieved June 15* (2020), p. 2021.
- [38] Shih-En Wei et al. “Convolutional pose machines”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2016, pp. 4724–4732.
- [39] Zhe Cao et al. “Realtime multi-person 2d pose estimation using part affinity fields”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017, pp. 7291–7299.
- [40] Tomas Simon et al. “Hand keypoint detection in single images using multiview bootstrapping”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2017, pp. 1145–1153.
- [41] Zhe Cao et al. “OpenPose: realtime multi-person 2D pose estimation using Part Affinity Fields”. In: *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 43.1 (2019), pp. 172–186.
- [42] István Sáráandi et al. “Metric-scale truncation-robust heatmaps for 3D human pose estimation”. In: *2020 15th IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition (FG 2020)*. IEEE. 2020, pp. 407–414.

- [43] István Sáráandi et al. “Metrabs: Metric-scale truncation-robust heatmaps for absolute 3d human pose estimation”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Biometrics, Behavior, and Identity Science* 3.1 (2020), pp. 16–30.
- [44] Dragomir Anguelov et al. “Scape: shape completion and animation of people”. In: *ACM SIGGRAPH 2005 Papers*. 2005, pp. 408–416.
- [45] Hanbyul Joo, Tomas Simon, and Yaser Sheikh. “Total capture: A 3d deformation model for tracking faces, hands, and bodies”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2018, pp. 8320–8329.
- [46] Hongyi Xu et al. “Ghum & ghuml: Generative 3d human shape and articulated pose models”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2020, pp. 6184–6193.
- [47] Federica Bogo et al. “Keep it SMPL: Automatic estimation of 3D human pose and shape from a single image”. In: *European conference on computer vision*. Springer. 2016, pp. 561–578.
- [48] Georgios Pavlakos et al. “Expressive body capture: 3d hands, face, and body from a single image”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019, pp. 10975–10985.
- [49] Vasileios Choutas et al. “Monocular expressive body regression through body-driven attention”. In: *European Conference on Computer Vision*. Springer. 2020, pp. 20–40.
- [50] Hanbyul Joo, Natalia Neverova, and Andrea Vedaldi. “Exemplar Fine-Tuning for 3D Human Model Fitting Towards In-the-Wild 3D Human Pose Estimation”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2004.03686* (2020).
- [51] Yu Rong, Takaaki Shiratori, and Hanbyul Joo. “Frankmocap: A monocular 3d whole-body pose estimation system via regression and integration”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021, pp. 1749–1759.
- [52] Angjoo Kanazawa et al. “End-to-end recovery of human shape and pose”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2018, pp. 7122–7131.

- [53] Dávid Rozenberszki et al. “3D Semantic Label Transfer in Human-Robot Collaboration”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2021, pp. 2602–2611.
- [54] Raul Mur-Artal, Jose Maria Martinez Montiel, and Juan D Tardos. “ORB-SLAM: a versatile and accurate monocular SLAM system”. In: *IEEE transactions on robotics* 31.5 (2015), pp. 1147–1163.
- [55] Andrew Szot et al. “Habitat 2.0: Training home assistants to rearrange their habitat”. In: *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 34 (2021).
- [56] Manolis Savva et al. “Habitat: A platform for embodied ai research”. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*. 2019, pp. 9339–9347.
- [57] Leif E Peterson. “K-nearest neighbor”. In: *Scholarpedia* 4.2 (2009), p. 1883.
- [58] Thomas Cover and Peter Hart. “Nearest neighbor pattern classification”. In: *IEEE transactions on information theory* 13.1 (1967), pp. 21–27.
- [59] James M Keller, Michael R Gray, and James A Givens. “A fuzzy k-nearest neighbor algorithm”. In: *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics* 4 (1985), pp. 580–585.
- [60] Pavel Senin. “Dynamic time warping algorithm review”. In: *Information and Computer Science Department University of Hawaii at Manoa Honolulu, USA* 855.1-23 (2008), p. 40.
- [61] Chotirat Ann Ratanamahatana and Eamonn Keogh. “Everything you know about dynamic time warping is wrong”. In: *Third workshop on mining temporal and sequential data*. Vol. 32. Citeseer. 2004.
- [62] Richard Szeliski. *Computer vision: algorithms and applications*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [63] David Frederick Malin. “Unsharp masking.” In: *AAS Photo Bulletin* 16 (1977), pp. 10–13.
- [64] Andrea Polesel, Giovanni Ramponi, and V John Mathews. “Image enhancement via adaptive unsharp masking”. In: *IEEE transactions on image processing* 9.3 (2000), pp. 505–510.

- [65] Charles Poynton. *Digital video and HD: Algorithms and Interfaces*. Elsevier, 2012.

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